

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

**GUIDE FOR SAMPLE SHIPMENT:
IMMUNOPHENOTYPE AND MINIMAL/MEASURABLE RESIDUAL
DISEASE STUDY**

This document aims to outline the specific instructions for the proper preparation, handling, transport, and shipment of clinical samples to the Reference Laboratory: “Childhood Cancer Cytomics Laboratory,” located at the Eastern Biomedical Research Center (CIBIOR) in Puebla. These samples are used for Immunophenotyping and Minimal/Measurable Residual Disease (MRD) studies for pediatric patients treated at ONCOCREAN centers with suspected or ongoing acute leukemia, using flow cytometry.

The most important aspects of the process and these guidelines are summarized in page 5, and are detailed below:

I. PROCESS FOR REQUESTING AN IMMUNOPHENOTYPE STUDY:

1. Send the study request via email with the following information:
 - a) Full name of the patient.
 - b) Hospital affiliation number.
 - c) Diagnostic suspicion/Oncohematological diagnosis
 - d) Clinical summary with details of the current condition.
 - e) Request Form.
 - f) Requesting ONCOCREAN service and corresponding contact information for sending results.

2. The request must be sent 24 hours prior to sample shipment from the Pediatric Coordination or the Head of the Onco/Hematology Service at the corresponding ONCOCREAN center, to the institutional email addresses.

3. Since the sample will be shipped via courier service, once the tracking number is obtained, it must be provided immediately to the email addresses mentioned above to ensure proper tracking of the sample.

4. Detail the morphological findings and FAB classification of the smear if available at the time of submission or update the information as soon as it becomes available via email.

II. PROCESS FOR REQUESTING MEASURABLE RESIDUAL DISEASE STUDY:

1. Send the study request via email with the following information:
 - a) Full name of the patient.

- b) Hospital affiliation number.
- c) Immunophenotype of diagnosis
- d) Request Form

2. The request must be sent 24 hours prior to sample shipment from the Pediatric Coordination or the Head of the Onco/Hematology Service at the corresponding ONCOCREAN center, to the institutional email addresses.

REQUIREMENTS FOR SAMPLE COLLECTION AND SHIPMENT

The sample must be taken in tubes with anticoagulant: EDTA K2 or K3 (Vacuum collection tube, Vacutainer purple or lilac lid) and must be properly labeled with the patient's name.

Volume for Immunophenotype: Min: 2 mL, Max: 5 mL
Volume for MRD: Min: 6 mL, Max: 10 mL

NOTE: It is important to indicate the order in which the tubes are taken when sending more than one sample tube.

*** The maximum volume indicated is intended to ensure increased sensitivity of the test**

1. Always use the "first pull" for flow cytometry. This minimizes hemodilution with peripheral blood, one of the main factors that impair the sensitivity of MRI.
2. Avoid the presence of clots or microclots in the sample, as even the smallest ones can cause a complete blockage in the equipment and affect the processing time and the delivery of results. Furthermore, neoplastic cells or populations of interest can become trapped in the clots and directly affect the results obtained.

The sample must be stored at room temperature (~22-25°C) between collection and shipment for processing.

Avoid shipping with refrigerant gels or any other foreign material that could contaminate the sample or compromise its integrity.

The sample must be taken before the application of any treatment (including the steroid window, according to the protocol). If the patient is currently undergoing any treatment, whether appropriate or not for the present condition, please indicate this on the request form.

3. Since the sample will be shipped via courier service, once the tracking number is obtained, it

must be provided immediately to the email addresses mentioned above to ensure proper tracking of the sample.

III. CHARACTERISTICS AND SPECIFICATIONS FOR SENDING SAMPLES FROM OUTSIDE THE LABORATORY.

SAMPLE PACKAGING:

I. PRIMARY PACKAGING:

1. The sample will be placed in a plastic bag for Hazardous Biological Infectious Waste (RPBI) of approximately 15 x 23 cm., with the red identification symbol of hazardous waste and hermetically sealed.

2. Wrap the bag in a soft/cushioning material that protects the sample from sudden impacts, such as: gauze, cotton, foam rubber, bubble wrap, etc.
3. The slides should be wrapped in cushioning material such as gauze, cotton, etc. to prevent fragmentation.

***NOTE:** In an effort to avoid pollution from single-use plastics, we suggest the following environmentally friendly options available in self-service stores and online services: Kraft paper cushioning, cardboard bubble wrap alternative, honeycomb paper, biodegradable padded bags, etc.

II. SECONDARY PACKAGING:

1. The package must be placed in a rigid container such as: cardboard box, plastic box, etc.
2. Secure the slides with tape to the secondary packaging to prevent damage, such as a cardboard box, and place them inside the secondary packaging of the sample.

C) SHIPMENT

The package must be sent with the following information. It is important that the complete address is provided exactly as described below:

The sample processing time recommended by international consensus is within the first 6 to 24 hours from collection to processing.

IMPORTANT: Prior to sending the samples, you must check the departure time in which your status guarantees Express shipping (24 hours) and guarantees delivery to the destination branch at 10:30am on the next business day.

Table with 3 columns: Sample collection and shipment, Sample arrival at laboratory, Express courier service. It details delivery times for Sunday to Thursday and Monday to Friday, including a note about Thursday submissions.

PLEASE CONSIDER THE IMSS HOLIDAY SCHEDULE WHEN GENERATING SUBMISSIONS

IV. SAMPLE IDENTIFICATION

- 1. All samples must be properly identified: each tube containing a sample must be labeled with the patient's name and a description of the sample type, whether peripheral blood (PB) or bone marrow (BM), and the order of collection when sending more than one tube.
2. Packages must be properly sealed and externally labeled (with the name and address of the sending hospital and the complete laboratory information).
3. Request forms must contain all the required information, including morphological findings (FAB classification) and blast percentage, as this data is essential for sample registration and processing.

V. RESULTS ISSUANCE TIME

- 1. Results are currently available within 48 business hours (starting from the date the sample arrives at the laboratory).
2. Samples are processed using a FACS Canto II and FACS Lyric Becton Dickinson™ flow cytometer, following EUROFLOW™ standards for both tests.
3. Results will be sent via institutional email, except in the event of unforeseen circumstances.

VI. STORAGE AND DISPOSAL OF SAMPLES

If there are any excess samples from the analysis, they will be stored for a period of 5 days. They will be kept under optimal conditions to maintain the stability of their properties; in case they are needed for any eventuality. After the stipulated period, as a general rule, the samples will be discarded in accordance with NOM-087-ECOL-SSA1-2002.

SUMMARY OF THE SHIPPING PROCEDURE

